

USE OF COORDINATE SYSTEMS AND GPS IN ARCHEOLOGY

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Annotation: *This thesis provides information about the use of the GIS system, work with maps, the geoinformation value of the GPS system and the scale of its operation.*

Keywords: *Geographic information system, map projection, mapping, GPS system, Google Earth program.*

Representing the surface of the globe on a mathematical basis is called cartographic projection, or in other words, regardless of whether we consider the globe as a sphere or a spheroid, it is necessary to transform the three-dimensional surface of the globe into a flat surface on the map based on mathematical rules. The mathematical basis of the map consists of a set of mathematical elements of the map, which defines the mathematical relationship between the surface on which they are depicted and the map. Projection, scale, geodetic base, as well as the composition system are the elements of the mathematical basis of the map. The basic mathematical elements of the map allow to correctly and precisely describe the surface of the earth on the plane based on certain mathematical rules. The scale determines the spatial limits of the cartographic model. The accuracy that can be measured on the map, the perfection of the content of the map, the accuracy of the cartographic image directly depends on its scale. The large or small scale of the map is determined by its purpose. When making a map, first meridian and parallel lines are drawn and they cross each other to form a cartographic grid. Then, plan base (base) points are dropped on this grid. After that, it is filled with other geographical objects. The cartographic grid of each individual map is drawn in a certain projection based on the purpose and task of this map. When drawing a cartographic grid, it is assumed that the area to be depicted is initially drawn on the surface of the globe at the scale of the map being created. The Earth's surface is depicted on flat paper, but when

a spherical (curved) surface is placed on a plane, various errors occur in the area, shape, angles and lengths of this surface on the map. In any case, when depicting the surface of the earth on a plane, two main requirements must be met, the uniformity and continuity of the image must be ensured. This means that, firstly, only one point on the map should correspond to each point on the earth's surface, and secondly, there should not be disconnected areas in the cartographic image. As a result of equal stretching or equal compression, the following errors appear in the cartographic image:

1. Length error;
2. Angle error;
3. Field error;
4. Form error.

Cartographic projections vary by uncorrelated errors and cartographic grids. Equilateral projections have no angular error. The value of the angles in all directions is preserved everywhere on the geographical maps made in such a projection. In equal-area projections, the proportionality between the area on the map and the area on the earth's surface is preserved. It is used to reduce errors in optional projections. In this case, equally spaced projections are used, and the constancy of the scale along the meridians and parallels is preserved, and shape, angle and area errors occur. All existing cartographic projections are classified according to the nature of errors and the method of constructing the cartographic grid.

Map (Greek: chartes - a sheet or papyrus on which a letter is written), card - a mathematically defined, reduced, generalized image of the Earth's surface, other celestial bodies or outer space. Objects located in them are displayed in the system of accepted conditional symbols.

Types of maps. Maps are divided into several types according to their scale, the extent of the territory depicted on them, their content, function and structure. Maps are divided into the following types depending on their scale: large scale, medium scale, small scale. Events and events are depicted in different degrees of accuracy on maps of different scales. Depending on what is depicted on them and the scale of the area, they are divided into the following types: star map, planet and Earth map, hemisphere maps, continents and oceans maps, natural geographical regions and seas maps, maps of countries, maps of administrative units, maps of special areas (reserves, tourist attractions), maps of cities and regions, districts. According to their content, maps are divided into two

major groups: general geographic maps and thematic maps. General geographic maps depict the main components of the geographical conditions of a place with the same accuracy. According to their function, maps are further divided into "scientific", "culture and propaganda", "technical", "travel maps", "educational maps".

Geographic information system (GIS) is a generalized computer system under the control of expert analysts, whose main tasks are to collect, store, manage, analyze, model and describe spatial-geographical data. Simply put, GIS incorporates cartography, statistical analysis, and a database. GIS is an interdisciplinary field and is widely used in cartography, remote sensing, land surveying, natural resource management, photogrammetry, geography, urban planning, aerial video, and local search systems. It is an internally positioned spatial information system designed for data management, cartographic images and analysis. GIS is a computer system designed to store, manage and describe geographical information of human activity and hardware. GIS was created for the first time in the 60s of the 20th century as a result of its use for military purposes in the USA and Canada. Later, this system is widely used as cadastral data.

GPS - Global Positioning System. This is a system developed by the USA, and satellites of the Earth (sputnik) transmit information to the earth at certain time intervals. It is possible to determine the distance from the satellite to the earth by the signal reaching it. The GPS receiver receives data from several satellites and determines where it is located. Using at least 5-9 satellites, the device can determine its location with an accuracy of 5-10 meters.

Google Earth (English: Google Earth) is a virtual globe, map, and geographic information program developed by Keyhole, Inc. under the name EarthViewer 3D. It was bought by Google in 2004. It displays a three-dimensional map of the earth using satellite photos.

Nowadays, we know that most of us have modern android mobile phones in our daily life. They work in the GSM network. In order for GPS devices to work, you need to insert a SIM card connected to the GSM network. Mobile phones have such sim cards. Most Android mobile phones also have a GPS device.

A program that receives their coordinates through GPS devices has been developed. The program was created in the Java programming language. Working principle: if the GPS device is present in the mobile phone, the program receives the x and y coordinates of the mobile phone through the GPS device. If the mobile phone is connected to the GSM

network without a GPS device, it receives the x and y coordinates of the nearest antenna. Information about the obtained coordinates is sent to the specified server. A program has been created on the server to process this data. In order to sort the data, the user must enter an id for himself. Otherwise, you may have trouble tracking the object. For this, each user must enter his id. If the "ID" serial number is the same as another user, the server will quickly send an error message to the user that this ID number is busy.

Sputniks usually send to earth:

Status message (fixes or errors);

Daily date;

Daily time;

Orbital data of all satellites; The exact time of all sent messages;

Astronomical tables (coordinates of the satellite in its current orbit)¹.

GPS - after receiving data from a satellite, the receiver determines its coordinates based on the laws of geometry by determining the distance between all satellites. In this case, it is enough to receive a signal from three satellites to determine two coordinates (latitude and longitude), and to determine the height coordinate relative to the earth, it is necessary to receive a signal from four satellites. To determine the distance between satellites, GPS is determined by the return time of the radio signal sent by the receiver. Of course, for this, the clocks of the satellite and the GPS receiver must be synchronized. One of the disadvantages of the GPS system is its "limited right". This shortcoming was that it was possible to detect objects from 30 to 100 m, and there was no possibility to detect objects that were more than 100 m away. But this situation did not go very far. This restriction has been canceled since May 1, 2000. Now this system can be used by different users from different points of the globe. Another drawback is the geometrical interdependence of satellites, radiation of radio signals (reflection of radio waves), ionospheric and atmospheric eclipses (seizure, delay) and others.

The GPS system provides an opportunity to determine the location of the object at various points on land, sea and near the ground. As mentioned in the previous sections, this system was created for military purposes. It later became clear that this system would help people achieve several "civic" goals. Today, the GPS system is widely used for navigation

¹ Информатика для гуманитариев: Учебное пособие/ Под.ред.В. Л. Акимова, Л.И. Бородкина. Москва-Саранск, 1998.-215 с

and cartographic purposes. Currently, the most widespread systems are Russian GLONASS and European GALILEO satellites. However, Russia's GLONASS satellite is now fully functional. Through the reception and processing of signals by this satellite, we solve many problems in the field of geodesy today. That's why most of the device manufacturing companies are now producing satellite receivers. An example of this is Topson Position System. These receivers are called GNSS receivers (Global Navigation Satellite System), as opposed to GPS receivers that only receive Navstar signals. This device uses processing methods of GNSS technology. A GPS device provides information such as time, latitude and longitude, altitude, and so on, when connected to a satellite.

2. You process that information. You get data about 10 times per second and store it in the MO (base).

3. Get satellite images or simple map images via Google Maps or Open Street Map.

For example, if we take the GPS Navigator on the Android phone, it will ask where the smartphone is located through the GPS device. Let's say 10 times every second or 1 second. After receiving the answer about the location, the program itself calculates based on the previous locations. You can use the most common Google Maps or OpenStreetMap maps if you want to show where it is on the map. Google Maps API is paid after certain requests. These API systems also provide street directions. You can calculate nearby streets by specifying GPS coordinates and develop a navigator.

Almost every modern device has an integrated GPS module. This antenna satellite signal is tuned for GPS positioning system. It was initially used in the United States for military purposes, but later it became possible for everyone to have a signal. The GPS-module device is a receiving antenna with an amplifier, but it is not possible to transmit. Receiving signals from satellites, the smartphone determines your location. Almost every modern at least once you enjoy a GPS navigation on your smartphone or tablet. The need for this can arise at any time for different professions and different professions. It is necessary for drivers, lettermen, hunters, fishermen and even ordinary pedestrians to find themselves in an unfamiliar city. To move on this site, you can build a route to locate the desired object on the map, and if you have proper Internet access in traffic jams.

Currently, based on the requirements of new information technologies, management systems related to the need to display on electronic maps have been created and are operating:

- A) Geoinformation systems
- B) Management systems
- C) Design systems

Information on the location of topographic, hydrographic, infrastructural objects of various sizes is used to solve social and technical problems. Representing this or that situation on the computer screen means displaying various graphic images. Geoinformation technologies are aimed at the practical application of data expressed in the form of a system of electronic maps and data processing environments of various nature. The main class of geoinformation systems is those that store geometric information and reflect the spatial aspect.

The main types of coordinate data are: Point (nodes, line), polygon (area), line (open), contour (closed, line). In practice, the same amount of data is used to build reactive objects. These are floating point, pseudo node, normal node, overlay, layer, etc. The basis of visual presentation of data using GAT technologies is based on the representation of vector and raster models using geometric vectors. In raster models, the object (region) is reflected in the spatial cells that make up the periodic grid.

1. A raster GPS device provides time, latitude and longitude, (longitude&altitude), altitude, and similar information when connected to a satellite.

2. You will receive and process the data. About 10 times per second, data is retrieved and stored in the data store.

3. Google Maps or Open Street Map takes a satellite image or a simple map image.

In conclusion, it can be said that the geographic information system and modern GPS-navigation create great opportunities in researching the field of archeology based on modern technologies and offer excellent functions to solve this complex task.

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